

Peripheral Neuropathy in Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease: A Case Controlled Cross-Sectional Study

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Abstract

Background: Chronic Obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) is not merely lung disease, it is considered as a multi system disorder with significant extrapulmonary manifestations. Peripheral neuropathy (PNP) is increasingly recognized as one of these manifestations, yet potentially under-recognized comorbidity. This study aims to determine the prevalence of PNP in COPD patients using nerve conduction study (NCS) and correlates its association with hypoxemia, smoking history, disease severity and frequent exacerbation of COPD.

Methods: One hundred participants were included in this study, divided into two subgroups (50 COPD patients, 50 age- and sex-matched healthy controls). Diagnosis and severity of COPD were based on GOLD 2023 criteria. All participants underwent a full clinical and neurological exam, including a standardized NCS of multiple upper and lower sensor/motor nerves.

Results: The prevalence of PNP was 32%. Sixteen of the fifty COPD patients subgroups were found to have varying degrees of PNP, while none in the controlled subgroup ($p < 0.001$). The majority of the affected group were clinically asymptomatic, 75% were having a silent PNP. The neuropathy was predominantly distal, length dependent and axonal, with the Sural nerve being the most affected (100%). Patients with these abnormally NCS results were significantly older ($p = 0.004$), had higher cumulative smoking exposure (>20 pack-years, $p = 0.043$), more severe advanced GOLD stages ($p = 0.022$), lower oxygen saturation ($SpO_2 < 88\%$, $p = 0.026$) and a higher frequent exacerbations ($p = 0.036$) compared to COPD patients with normal NCS.

Conclusion: Peripheral neuropathy (PNP) is a common, predominantly subclinical and considered as systemic manifestation of COPD. It is largely associated with chronic hypoxemia, severe COPD disease, heavy smoking and frequent exacerbations. Depending on routine clinical assessment for the neuropathy is insufficient. Electrophysiological study is essential for early identification, which may guide a more proper management plan improving the quality of life.

Introduction

Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD) is a progressive pulmonary disorder characterized by persistent respiratory illness and airflow limitations [1]. It is well known in the recent few decades that COPD is a heterogeneous, multisystem disease with a wide range of significant extrapulmonary manifestations affecting

different systems such as cardiovascular, muscular, endocrine and neuropsychiatric [2-4]. Among these manifestations, PNP represents a significant comorbidity, yet under-recognized contributing to disease disability and reducing the quality of life [5,6]. The exact pathophysiology linking COPD and PNP is multifactorial. Chronic hypoxia which frequently

More Information

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Keywords:

Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease, Peripheral Neuropathy, Hypoxemia, Smoking, Nerve Conduction Study, Systemic Inflammation.

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encountered in COPD patients and it's a hallmark of advanced COPD, can impair mitochondrial energy metabolism in neuronal cells and Schwann cells, disrupting nervous system function and damaging myelin integrity [7-10]. Systemic inflammation which is considered a cornerstone of COPD, characterized by elevated cytokines such as TNF- α , IL-6 and CRP can precipitate microvascular endothelial and neuronal injury [11,12]. Furthermore, smoking tobacco is considered a major cause for COPD besides air pollution and biomass fuel [13]. For example, smoking cigarettes contains several thousands of chemical components from which about two hundreds harmful materials are absorbed into blood circulation and internal tissue. These components induce oxidative stress, vasoconstriction, alter the immune system and induce direct nerve injury [14-17]. Nutritional deficiencies, which are commonly encountered in advanced COPD stages may also contribute to neuropathic changes [18,19]. While age is considered a common risk factor for a different condition, COPD, vascular disease and PNP all share the age as being one of the independent risk factors [20]. Han et al.(2017) reported in their study that patients with COPD experience acute exacerbations of COPD up to three times per year, AECOPD are associated with several harmful effects on multi-organs such as the nervous and muscular systems. Infections, electrolyte disturbance, systemic inflammation, hypercapnia and invasive ventilation all contributed to induce nerve damage [21-23]. Despite these plausible mechanisms, the prevalence and clinical correlates of PNP in COPD remain insufficiently characterized, with reported rates varying widely from 5% to 95% depending on diagnostic methods [24-26]. Clinical assessment alone often fails to detect subclinical nerve involvement, underscoring the need for objective electrophysiological evaluation [13].

Aim of the Study

This study aimed to determine the prevalence of PNP in COPD patients using nerve conduction study (NCS) and to explore its relationship with chronic hypoxia, disease severity (GOLD staging), smoking history and acute exacerbations.

Patients and Methods

Study Design and Setting

A case-control/cross-sectional was conducted in the Department of Internal Medicine and Neurophysiology Unit at Merjan teaching hospital, Babylon, Iraq, over a ten months period (January- August 2025).

Study Population

The study consisted of 100 participants divided into two groups:

1. COPD group (n=50): diagnosed COPD patients attending outpatients or inpatients.

2. Control Group (n=50): Age- and sex-matched apparently healthy individuals with no history of chronic respiratory or neurological disease.

Inclusion Criteria

COPD Group

Patients were included by the following criteria according to GOLD 2023 (12):

- Age older than 40 years
- Confirmed diagnosis of COPD based on GOLD 2023

Post bronchodilators FEV1/FVC <0.7

Control Group

Age- and sex-matched apparently healthy individuals with no history of chronic respiratory or neurological disease.

Exclusion Criteria

Both groups were excluded if they had the following: Diabetes mellitus, Alcohol use, Chronic kidney disease, Chronic liver disease, Thyroid disease, other known causes of neuropathy (e.g., cervical/lumbosacral radiculopathy).

Data Collection

1. **Sociodemographic and Clinical Data:** Age, sex, smoking status (pack-years, categorized as <20 and \geq 20), and oxygen saturation (SpO₂, categorized as <88%, 88-92%, >92%), frequent acute exacerbations (more than two episodes in the past year).

2. **COPD Severity Classification:** Classified according to GOLD 2023 stages (1-4) based on post-bronchodilator FEV1. Pulmonary function tests were performed using standard spirometry.

3. **Neurological Evaluation:** Full neurological examination (muscle strength, light touch, pinprick, vibration, reflexes) and assessment of neuropathic symptoms (numbness, burning, tingling).

4. **Nerve Conduction Study (NCS)** Performed by neurophysiologist specialist at the neurophysiology unit, using a Nihon Kohden NCS device. Nerves studied included: Median (motor+sensory), Ulnar (motor+sensory), Peroneal (motor), Tibial (motor), and Sural (sensory). Parameters recorded were amplitude, distal latency, conduction velocity, and F-wave latency. Skin temperature was maintained >32°C, sensory studies: antidromic stimulation, motor studies: stimulation at wrist/ elbow/ ankle.

Definition Of Abnormal NCS

NCS was considered abnormal if Amplitude < 2.5 SD the lower limit, Conduction Velocity CV reduced and prolonged Latency/F-wave Latency. PNP was diagnosed when equal or more than 2 nerves showed abnormalities [27].

Ethical Considerations

Written consent from the participants was obtained before inclusion, and patient information was maintained to keep confidentiality and privacy. The study protocol was approved by the Ethical Committee

of Merjan Teaching Hospital and the Iraqi Board Council for Medical Specialties.

Results

The study included 100 participants: 50 patients with COPD and 50 healthy controls. The two groups were comparable regarding age and sex distribution. Most participants were aged 50–69 years, with no significant difference in age categories ($p > 0.9$). Males predominated in both groups (82.0% in controls vs 86.0% in COPD), with no significant sex difference ($p = 0.6$).

Smoking characteristics differed significantly between groups. Current smoking was more prevalent among COPD patients than controls (60.0% vs 32.0%), while non-smokers were observed only in the control group (24.0%) ($p < 0.001$). Among smokers, heavy smoking exposure (>20 pack-years) was markedly more frequent in COPD patients (82.0%) compared with controls (10.0%), whereas lighter exposure (<20 pack-years) predominated among controls ($p < 0.001$) (Table 1).

Table 1: Sociodemographic Factors between the Study Groups (N = 100)

Characteristic	Control, N = 50 ¹	COPD, N = 50 ¹	p-value ²
Age, years			
<50	3 (6.0%)	3 (6.0%)	>0.9
50-59	24 (48.0%)	22 (44.0%)	
60-69	19 (38.0%)	19 (38.0%)	
>70	4 (8.0%)	6 (12.0%)	
Sex			
Male	41 (82.0%)	43 (86.0%)	0.6
Female	9 (18.0%)	7 (14.0%)	
Smoking status			
Current smoker	16 (32.0%)	30 (60.0%)	<0.001
Ex-smoker	22 (44.0%)	20 (40.0%)	
Non-smoker	12 (24.0%)	0 (0.0%)	
Pack, years (among the smokers)			
>20	5 (10.0%)	41 (82.0%)	<0.001
<20	33 (66.0%)	9 (18.0%)	

Note: ¹ n (%); ² Fisher's exact test; Pearson's Chi-squared test

Nerve Conduction Study Parameters

NCS revealed widespread abnormalities in the COPD group across all tested nerves. Compared to controls, COPD patients showed significantly reduced compound

muscle and sensory nerve action potential amplitudes, prolonged distal latencies, and slower conduction velocities ($p < 0.001$ for most parameters) in the Median, Ulnar, Peroneal, Tibial, and Sural nerves (Tables 2-6).

Table 2: Comparison of Median Nerve Motor and Sensory Conduction Parameters between Patients with COPD and Healthy Controls.

Median Nerve	Control, N = 50 ¹	COPD, N = 50 ¹	p-value ²
Motor conduction			
Amplitude (mV)	11.0 ± 2.1	7.2 ± 1.8	<0.001
Distal latency (ms)	2.4 ± 0.4	3.2 ± 0.6	<0.001
Conduction velocity (m/s)	60.9 ± 5.2	56.5 ± 7.1	<0.001
F-wave (ms)	23.0 ± 1.3	24.9 ± 3.6	0.001
Sensory conduction			
Amplitude (mv)	49.0 ± 17.4	31.4 ± 11.8	<0.001
Peak Latency (ms)	2.1 ± 0.5	3.0 ± 0.7	<0.001
Velocity (m/s)	60.9 ± 6.0	53.9 ± 7.9	<0.001

¹ Mean ± SD
² Welch Two Sample t-test

Note: ¹ Mean ± SD; ² Welch Two Sample t-test

Table 3: Comparison of Ulnar Nerve Motor and Sensory Conduction Parameters between Patients with COPD and Healthy Controls

Ulnar Nerve	Control, N = 50 ¹	COPD, N = 50 ¹	p-value ²
Motor conduction			
Amplitude (mV)	9.4 ± 1.4	7.7 ± 1.2	<0.001
Distal latency (ms)	2.1 ± 0.5	2.7 ± 0.7	<0.001
Conduction velocity (m/s)	63.0 ± 6.7	59.3 ± 6.5	0.005
Sensory conduction			
Amplitude (mv)	53.3 ± 16.9	29.4 ± 12.2	<0.001
Peak Latency (ms)	2.1 ± 0.4	2.7 ± 0.6	<0.001
Velocity (m/s)	67.6 ± 14.4	58.7 ± 10.0	<0.001

Note: ¹ Mean ± SD; ² Welch Two Sample t-test

Table 4: Comparison of Peroneal Nerve Motor Conduction Parameters between Patients with COPD and Healthy Controls

Peroneal Nerve	Control, N = 50 ¹	COPD, N = 50 ¹	p-value ²
Motor conduction			
Amplitude (mV)	5.0 ± 1.1	3.6 ± 1.2	<0.001
Distal latency (ms)	3.2 ± 0.5	5.0 ± 0.8	<0.001
Conduction velocity (m/s)	63.5 ± 5.7	51.7 ± 4.7	<0.001

Note: ¹ Mean ± SD; ² Welch Two Sample t-test

Table 5: Comparison of Tibial Nerve Motor Conduction Parameters between Patients with COPD and Healthy Controls

Tibial Nerve	Control, N = 50 ¹	COPD, N = 50 ¹	p-value ²
Motor conduction			
Amplitude (mV)	11.0 ± 2.8	5.9 ± 1.3	<0.001
Distal latency (ms)	3.7 ± 0.4	4.8 ± 0.6	<0.001
Conduction velocity (m/s)	61.9 ± 6.0	51.6 ± 3.7	<0.001
F- wave (ms)	44.8 ± 2.0	48.4 ± 4.1	<0.001

Note: ¹ Mean ± SD; ² Welch Two Sample t-test

Table 6: Comparison of Sural Nerve Sensory Conduction Parameters between Patients with COPD and Healthy Controls

Sural Nerve	Control, N = 50 ¹	COPD, N = 50 ¹	p-value ²
Sensory conduction			
Amplitude (mv)	23.2 ± 5.8	16.2 ± 10.8	<0.001
Peak Latency (ms)	2.7 ± 0.4	3.7 ± 0.8	<0.001
Velocity (m/s)	57.1 ± 6.6	48.3 ± 7.1	<0.001

Note: ¹ Mean ± SD; ² Welch Two Sample t-test

Overall Nerve Conduction Findings

All control participants (100%) had normal nerve conduction studies. In contrast, abnormal nerve conduction was detected in 16 COPD patients (32.0%),

while 34 patients (68.0%) had normal findings. This difference was statistically significant (p < 0.001), indicating a strong association between COPD and peripheral nerve involvement (Table 7).

Table 7: Result of Nerve Conduction Study among the Study Groups

Characteristic	Control, N = 50 ¹	COPD, N = 50 ¹	p-value ²
Nerve conduction study			
Normal	50 (100.0%)	34 (68.0%)	<0.001
Abnormal	0 (0.0%)	16 (32.0%)	

Note: ¹ Mean ± SD; ² Welch Two Sample t-test

Pattern of Neuropathy and Clinical Correlation

Among COPD patients with abnormal nerve conduction studies (n = 16), the pattern was predominantly length-dependent distal neuropathy. The sural nerve was affected in all cases (100%), followed by the median nerve (68.8%) and ulnar nerve (43.8%). Lower limb motor nerve involvement (peroneal and tibial nerves) was observed in 25.0% of patients.

Despite significant electrophysiological abnormalities, most patients were clinically asymptomatic. Twelve patients (75.0%) reported no neurological symptoms, while a minority experienced sensory complaints such as burning, numbness, or tingling. Neurological examination was normal in 75.0% of patients, with only a small proportion showing reflex abnormalities, muscle wasting, or sensory deficits (Table 8).

Table 8: Description of the Most Affected Nerves and Neurological Examination among COPD Patients with Abnormal Nerve Conductive Study (N = 16)

Characteristic	N = 16 ¹
Affected nerve	
Sural nerve	16 (100.0%)
Median nerve	11 (68.8%)
Ulnar nerve	7 (43.8%)
Peroneal nerve	4 (25.0%)
Tibial nerve	4 (25.0%)
Neurological symptom	
No symptoms	12 (75.0%)
Burning, and numbness	2 (12.5%)
Tingling sensation, burning, and numbness	1 (6.2%)
Tingling sensation, and numbness	1 (6.2%)
Neurological examination	
Unremarkable	12 (75.0%)
Reflex abnormality, and muscle wasting	2 (12.5%)
Reflex abnormality	1 (6.2%)
Reflex abnormality, and reduce pin prick sensation	1 (6.2%)

Note: ¹n (%)

Factors Associated with Abnormal Nerve Conduction in COPD

Compared with COPD patients with normal nerve conduction studies, those with abnormal findings were significantly older (p = 0.004) and had greater cumulative smoking exposure, with all patients having >20 pack-years (p = 0.043). Disease severity was significantly higher in the abnormal group, with a

greater proportion of severe and very severe COPD according to GOLD classification (p = 0.022).

Patients with abnormal nerve conduction also had lower oxygen saturation levels, with a higher prevalence of SpO₂ <88% (p = 0.026), and experienced more frequent exacerbations in the preceding year (≥2 exacerbations in 68.8% vs 35.3%, p = 0.036). Sex distribution and smoking duration did not differ significantly between groups (Table 9).

Table 9: Comparison of Demographic, Smoking, and Disease Severity Characteristics between COPD Patients with Abnormal and Normal Nerve Conduction Studies (N = 50)

Characteristic	Abnormal, N = 16 ¹	Normal, N = 34 ¹	p-value ²
Age, years			
<50	0 (0.0%)	3 (8.8%)	0.004
50-59	3 (18.8%)	19 (55.9%)	
60-69	8 (50.0%)	11 (32.4%)	
>70	5 (31.2%)	1 (2.9%)	
Sex			
Male	14 (87.5%)	29 (85.3%)	>0.9
Female	2 (12.5%)	5 (14.7%)	
Smoking status			
Current smoker	13 (81.2%)	17 (50.0%)	0.062

Characteristic	Abnormal, N = 16 ¹	Normal, N = 34 ¹	p-value ²
Ex-smoker	3 (18.8%)	17 (50.0%)	
Non-smoker	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	
Pack, years			
>20	16 (100.0%)	25 (73.5%)	0.043
<20	0 (0.0%)	9 (26.5%)	
Duration of smoking			
<5 years	9 (56.2%)	19 (55.9%)	>0.9
5-10 years	5 (31.2%)	12 (35.3%)	
>10	2 (12.5%)	3 (8.8%)	
Gold classification			
Mild	0 (0.0%)	4 (11.8%)	0.022
Moderate	6 (37.5%)	23 (67.6%)	
Severe	7 (43.8%)	6 (17.6%)	
Very severe	3 (18.8%)	1 (2.9%)	
Oxygen saturation (SpO₂)			
<88%	7 (43.8%)	5 (14.7%)	0.026
88%- 92%	6 (37.5%)	10 (29.4%)	
>92%	3 (18.8%)	19 (55.9%)	
Exacerbation in last year			
None or one	5 (31.2%)	22 (64.7%)	0.036
Equal or more than two	11 (68.8%)	12 (35.3%)	

Note: ¹n (%); ²Fisher's exact test

Discussion

This present study shows a prevalence of 32% comparable with other study Kahnert et al. (2020) reported that approximately 22% of the patients in the COSYCONET study were found to have electrophysiological abnormalities, this supported by the narrative review conducted by Odajiu et al. (2022) Which show similar results [6,26]. While earlier results reported a prevalence ranging from as low as 5% to high 95%, this difference can be explained by the strict inclusion criteria, study design and the use of modern electrophysiological studies not solely depending on the clinical assessment of neuropathy [24-26]. Studies that depend solely on clinical assessment where with lowest prevalence, while using electrophysiological studies have shown a much increase in the prevalence. In the present study 75% of the abnormal NCS results were found to have no neurological symptoms, not reporting obvious symptoms such as tingling, numbness and burning sensation with normal neurological exam. These findings are consistent with Yrtgun et al. (2020), which reported that most of the COPD patients with PNP are asymptomatic [13]. This phenomenon can be explained by the predominance of sensory axonal neuronal involvement, where NCS abnormalities may precede the overt neurological presentation [28]. This underscores the importance of electrophysiological testing in detecting early nerve involvement that would otherwise remain unrecognized during routine clinical evaluation. Our

cohort revealed that a length dependent, distal neuropathy involvement was the most electrophysiological abnormality encountered. With the Sural nerve being the most affected (100.0%), followed by median nerve (68.8%) to a lesser extent the ulnar nerve (43.8%), while the motor involvement in the tibial and peroneal nerves were 25% for each (table 8). This pattern is characteristic of axonal poly neuropathy; these findings are consistent with Kahnert et al. (2020) And Odajiu et al. (2022), both described distal axonal sensory neuropathy as the most electrophysiological abnormality encountered [6,26]. While Sural nerve exclusivity involvement supports the observation that lower limb nerves are the earlier nerves to be affected due to their length and higher metabolic demand [29]. Similar findings reported by [8], that Sural nerves are the earlier nerves to be affected even in the absence of severe respiratory impairment in COPD patients. The present study marks patients with abnormal electrophysiological study who seem to be older, yielding a significant difference in age distribution (p=0.004). While age is considered an independent risk factor for both PNP and COPD [30,31]. However, the absence of NCS abnormality in the aged match control group, suggesting that age alone doesn't explain the observed findings. Instead, age with other comorbidities that are frequently encountered in COPD patients such as smoking, chronic hypoxia and frequent acute exacerbations of COPD can act synergistically, increasing neuronal involvement. These observations

are consistent with the findings of Arisoy et al.(2021) found significantly higher neuropathic changes in COPD patients compared with age-matched controls, suggesting that COPD related systemic inflammation and hypoxemia contribute to nerve involvement beyond the effect of age alone [20]. Although smoking status did not differ significantly between COPD patients with and without neuropathy, cumulative smoking exposure measured by pack-years was significantly associated with abnormal NCS. All patients with neuropathy had a smoking history exceeding 20 pack-years ($p=0.043$), these findings are consistent with previous reports that cumulative rather than duration are associated with more pronounced neuronal involvement [16,17]. These mechanisms may act with systemic inflammation and chronic hypoxia that are related to COPD promoting neuronal injury. In this analysis we found that disease severity by GOLD classification was more advanced among those with abnormal studies, who mainly had severe or very severe COPD, whereas normal NCS predominates in the mild to a lesser extent in moderate COPD groups that differ significantly ($p = 0.022$). These observations correlate with both Agrawal et al. [25] and Arisoy et al. [20], both reported that the prevalence of PNP increases as the disease progresses to an advanced stage. Our findings demonstrate oxygen saturation was poorer in the affected group, with a higher proportion having $SpO_2 < 88\%$ and fewer proportion with $SpO_2 > 92\%$ this differ significantly ($p = 0.026$), Chronic hypoxemia has been shown to impair mitochondrial energy metabolism in neurons and Schwann cells, disrupt myelin maintenance, and promote axonal degeneration [7-9]. This supports the hypothesis that hypoxia that is reported in advanced stage COPD plays a central role in the development of neuropathy. Our cohort highlighted that COPD patients who experienced more than two acute exacerbations in the preceding year, were found to have a higher incidence with PNP compared to those who have experienced one or none exacerbation; this difference is statistically significant ($p = 0.036$). These findings correlate with other studies reporting that acute exacerbations are associated with harmful effects on organs such as the nervous system including infections, electrolytes disturbance and systemic inflammation [21,22]. While in a recent study conducted by Maignan et al. (2019), COPD patients who have acute exacerbations are experiencing an increase in pain owing it to an increase in neuronal damage [23]. Although our data didn't measure inflammatory biomarkers or nutritional status, the absence of these data is a limitation to our study and suggests that future investigation should include these data for a better understanding. The findings of this study highlighted the increased need for clinical awareness of peripheral neuropathy in COPD

patients. Focusing on elderly patients, those with advanced disease stage, chronic hypoxia, cumulative smoking (pack year more than 20) or those with frequent exacerbations may benefit from targeted neurological assessment, smoking cessation programmes, optimization of oxygen therapy, nutritional assessment and rehabilitation programs aimed at maintaining the health of nervous system and improving quality of life as suggested by previous authors [6,13,26].

Strength and Limitation

The strengths of our study include a well matched control group, strict inclusion/exclusion criteria, using a standardized nerve conduction study (NCS) for neurological assessment, comparable results with different recent studies and comprehensive assessment of disease severity and risk factors. Limitations include the relatively small sample size, single-center design and cross-sectional design of the study. Additionally, biochemical markers of inflammation and nutritional status were not assessed in our cohort as discussed earlier in this chapter.

Conclusion

Peripheral neuropathy is a common manifestation of a broader systemic manifestation of COPD, yet it is predominantly subclinical requiring careful assessment of the nervous system. The prevalence observed in this study is comparable to that reported in contemporary electrophysiological studies. Peripheral neuropathy is associated with older ages, higher cumulative smoking (pack year more than 20), advanced COPD stage according to GOLD, chronic hypoxemia and frequent exacerbations. These findings are consistent with existing literature and further support the recognition of PNP as an important systemic manifestation of COPD. Routine neurological examination and clinical assessment alone is insufficient to detect the early neurological involvement, and nerve conduction studies (NCS) remain essential for identifying subclinical disease and guiding comprehensive patient management.

References

- [1] Agustí A, Celli BR, Criner GJ, Halpin DMG, Anzueto A, Barnes PJ, et al. Global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease 2023 Report: GOLD Executive Summary. *American Journal of Respiratory and Critical Care Medicine*. 2023;207(7):819-837.
- [2] Corlateanu A, Covantev S, Mathioudakis AG, Botnaru V, Cazzola M, Siafakas N. Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and stroke. *COPD*. 2018;15(4):405–13. doi:10.1080/15412555.2018.1464551
- [3] Huang YL, Min J, Li GH, et al. The clinical study of comorbidities and systemic inflammation in COPD. *J Sichuan Univ (Med Sci Ed)*. 2019;50(1):88–92.
- [4] Xiang Y, Luo X. Extrapulmonary comorbidities associated with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease:

- a review. *Int J Chron Obstruct Pulmon Dis.* 2024;19:567–78. doi:10.2147/COPD.S447739.
- [5] Öncel Ç, Baser S, Çam M, Akdağ B, Taspınar B, Evyapan F. Peripheral neuropathy in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *COPD.* 2010;7(1):11–16. doi:10.3109/15412550903499480.
- [6] Odajiu I, Covantsev S, Sivapalan P, Mathioudakis AG, Jensen JS, Davidescu EI, Chatzimavridou-Grigoriadou V, Corlateanu A. Peripheral neuropathy: a neglected cause of disability in COPD – a narrative review. *Respir Med.* 2022;201:106952. doi:10.1016/j.rmed.2022.106952.
- [7] André-Lévigne D, Pignel R, Boet S, Jaquet V, Kalbermatten DF, Madduri S. Role of Oxygen and Its Radicals in Peripheral Nerve Regeneration: From Hypoxia to Physoxia to Hyperoxia. *Int J Mol Sci.* 2024;25(4):2030. doi:10.3390/ijms25042030.
- [8] Hervera A, De Virgiliis F, Palmisano I, Zhou L, Tantardini E, Kong G, et al. Reactive oxygen species regulate axonal regeneration through the release of exosomal NADPH oxidase 2 complexes into injured axons. *Nat Cell Biol.* 2018;20(3):307–19.
- [9] Vervust W, Ghysels A. Oxygen storage in stacked phospholipid membranes under an oxygen gradient as a model for myelin sheaths. *Adv Exp Med Biol.* 2022;1395:301–7.
- [10] Zysman M, Deslee G, Perez T, Burgel PR, Le Rouzic O, Brinchault-Rabin G, et al. Burden and characteristics of severe chronic hypoxemia in a real-world cohort of subjects with COPD. *Int J Chron Obstruct Pulmon Dis.* 2021;16:1275–84. doi:10.2147/COPD.S295381
- [11] Barnes PJ. Inflammatory mechanisms in patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *J Allergy Clin Immunol.* 2016;138(1):16–27. doi:10.1016/j.jaci.2016.05.011.
- [12] Pournaras N, Andersson A, Kovach MA, et al. Glucose homeostasis in relation to neutrophil mobilization in smokers with COPD. *Int J Chron Obstruct Pulmon Dis.* 2022;17:1179–1194. doi:10.2147/COPD.S353753
- [13] Yurtgün H, Tülek B, Ekmekçi H, Kanat F, Süerdem M. Subclinical peripheral neuropathy in patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease without hypoxemia. *Eurasian J Pulmonol.* 2020;22(3):175–179.
- [14] Wahl E. Acute stimulation of mesenchymal stem cells with cigarette smoke extract affects their migration, differentiation, and paracrine potential. *Sci Rep.* 2016;6:22957. doi:10.1038/srep22957.
- [15] Lee J., Taneja V., Vassallo R. Cigarette smoking and inflammation: cellular and molecular mechanisms. *J Dent Res.* 2012;91(2):142–149. doi:10.1177/0022034511421200.
- [16] Rinker B. The effect of cigarette smoking on functional recovery following peripheral nerve ischemia/reperfusion injury. *Microsurgery.* 2011;31(1):59–65. doi:10.1002/micr.20820.
- [17] Wang D., Gao T., Zhao Y. Nicotine exerts neuroprotective effects by attenuating local inflammatory cytokine production following crush injury to rat sciatic nerves. *Eur Cytokine Netw.* 2019;30(2):59–66. doi:10.1684/ecn.2019.0426.
- [18] Tuna T, Samur G. The role of nutrition and nutritional supplements in the prevention and treatment of malnutrition in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease: current approaches in nutrition therapy. *Curr Nutr Rep.* 2025;14(1):21. doi:10.1007/s13668-025-00613-8. PMID: PMC11762775.
- [19] Staff NP, Windebank AJ. Peripheral neuropathy due to vitamin deficiency, toxins, and medications. *Continuum (Minneapolis, Minn).* 2014 Oct;20(5):1293–306. doi:10.1212/01.CON.0000455880.06675.5a. PMID: PMC4208100.
- [20] Arisoy A, Yilgor A, Uney IH. Association between severe chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and polyneuropathy. *Med Sci Monit.* 2021;27:e932690. doi:10.12659/MSM.932690.
- [21] Ko FW, Chan KP, Hui DS, Goddard JR, Rainer TH, Sung JY, et al. Acute exacerbation of COPD. *Respirology.* 2016;21(7):1152–65. doi:10.1111/resp.12780.
- [22] Han MK, Quibrera PM, Carretta EE, Barr RG, Bleeker ER, Bowler RP, et al. Frequency of exacerbations in patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease: an analysis of the SPIROMICS cohort. *Lancet Respir Med.* 2017;5(8):619–26. doi:10.1016/S2213-2600(17)30207-2.
- [23] Maignan M, Chauny J-M, Daoust R, Duc L, Mabiála-Makele P, Collomb-Muret R, et al. Pain during exacerbation of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease: a prospective cohort study. *PLoS ONE.* 2019;14(5):e0217370. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0217370.
- [24] Divo M, Cote C, de Torres JP, Casanova C, Marin JM, Pinto-Plata V, et al. Comorbidities and risk of mortality in patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med.* 2012;186(2):155–161. doi:10.1164/rccm.201201-0034OC.
- [25] Agrawal D, Vohra R, Gupta PP, Sood S. Subclinical peripheral neuropathy in stable middle-aged patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *Singap Med J.* 2007;48(10):887–894.
- [26] Kahnert K, Föhrenbach M, Lucke T, Alter P, Trudzinski FT, Bals R, et al. The impact of COPD on polyneuropathy: results from the German COPD cohort COSYCONET. *Respir Res.* 2020;21(1):28. doi:10.1186/s12931-020-1293-6.

- [27] Tankisi H, Pugdahl K, Fuglsang-Frederiksen A. Electrodiagnostic Testing of Large Fiber Polyneuropathies: A Review of Existing Guidelines. *Journal of Clinical Neurophysiology*. 2020 Jul;37(4):277-287. doi: 10.1097/WNP.0000000000000674
- [28] Karvelas K, Rydberg L, Oswald M. Electrodiagnostics and clinical correlates in acquired polyneuropathies. *PM&R*. 2013;5(5 Suppl):S56–62. doi: 10.1016/j.pmrj.2013.03.030.
- [29] Rabe KF, Rennard S, Martinez FJ, et al. Targeting type 2 inflammation and epithelial alarmins

in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease: a biologics outlook. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med*. 2023;208(4):395–405. doi:10.1164/rccm.202303-0455CI.

[30] Brisset M, Nicolas G. Peripheral neuropathies and aging. *Geriatr Psychol Neuropsychiatr Vieil*. 2018;16(4):409–13. doi:10.1684/pnv.2018.0768.

[31] Hicks CW, Wang D, Windham BG, et al. Prevalence of peripheral neuropathy defined by monofilament insensitivity in middle-aged and older adults in two US cohorts. *Sci Rep*. 2021;11:19159. doi:10.1038/s41598-021-98565-w.

